

NAGRIKAL

CITIZENS VOICES
FOR AND FROM
SMALL CITIES

**MAY
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CONTEXTUALISING SMALLER CITIES IN CLIMATE CHANGE

Part of Nagrikal Series -

Frontlines of climate change: Small and mid-sized Cities

A study on where small Indian cities stand in terms of climate change impacts and data availability

NAGRIKA

About Nagrika

Nagrika is a think-tank enabling citizens in small and mid-sized cities. We create knowledge that shapes unique, authentic and resilient cities. Through this knowledge, we mainstream the voice of citizens in decision making.

We co-create accessible and free knowledge resources for citizens and city governments. We have been creating knowledge about smaller cities from a small city. Much of this knowledge did not exist before and we strongly believe that what we are creating is needed by many but created by none. Our interventions have made it possible to understand these cities better. Slowly and steadily, our work has ensured that smaller cities become part of policy agendas of urban policy making.

We build a sense of ownership and community in small towns while strengthening city - policy - citizen relationship by demystifying public policy. Our activities include creating and amplifying voices from smaller cities, putting spotlight on developments in smaller cities, analyzing larger trends for their impact on smaller cities and various other initiatives that push the boundaries of thought and action in our small towns.

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Our Partners

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This report is a living document and will be regularly updated. It is being informed by our ongoing research and co-created knowledge from various actors and institutions across multiple smaller cities.

About the Series

This Nagrikal Series examines the relationship between climate change and cities, especially small and mid-sized cities*. The series attempts to explore the dual roles of such cities- cities as contributors to and sufferers of climate change.

This Nagrikal series discusses some of the important impacts of climate change, like poor air quality, rising sea levels, rising temperatures, and increasing heatwaves. It serves as an explainer of how climate change induces these impacts in our cities. Highlighting the limited share of knowledge about small cities, climate data availability, and monitoring, this series urges us to rethink the future of small cities in the face of climate change. By bringing forth the facts and figures that are less talked about, we hope to shift the discourse from our current understanding in an effort to build resilient small cities.

From defining the role of cities, especially the smaller cities, in climate change to exploring the share of such cities in research studies, climate data availability, and monitoring, the series aligns with our objective of creating knowledge for smaller cities to drive meaningful action. The series is divided into four parts. Part one explains the relationship between cities and climate change; Part two talks about the declining air quality in small cities; Part three focuses on the rise in temperatures and heatwaves; and Part four highlights the cities that are at risk of sea level rise. Parts two, three, and four use small cities as case studies to explain the consequences of the respective impacts. Some of the key insights and findings from each of the parts are shared in the next section.

We invite readers to engage with the findings of this report and join us in the collective effort to reimagine the future of small cities in the face of climate change. We believe that stakeholders at every level can make a significant change by utilising the insights provided in this publication. By understanding the city specific challenges, let us co-create innovative solutions to combat climate change impacts for a sustainable and resilient future.

We hope that this report will not just inform but also initiate a conversation about the challenges faced by small cities with regards to climate change in the policy discourse and climate action strategies, which is currently missing.

**Small and Mid-sized in this report refer to cities that have a population of up to 2.5 million.*

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List of Abbreviations

°C	Degree Celsius
GHGs	Greenhouse Gases
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
CH ₄	Methane
O ₃	Ozone
N ₂ O	Nitrous Oxide
CFCs	Chlorofluorocarbons
ppm	parts per million
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
GtCO ₂ -eq	Gigatonnes Carbon Dioxide equivalent
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
CEEW	Council on Energy, Environment and Water
MtCO ₂ e	Metric tons of Carbon Dioxide equivalent
NDC	Nationally Determined Contributions
m	Metre
mm	Millimetre

Glossary

Climate	Average of weather conditions or patterns (such as temperature, wind, cloud cover, and precipitation) for a particular region that occurs for a long period of time, usually 30 years.
Weather	The state of atmosphere at a smaller region for a particular time, usually on a day-to-day basis.
Climate Change	Long term shifts in temperature and weather patterns for a particular region from their average (also known as normal) weather patterns.
Greenhouse Gases	The gases in the atmosphere which are not static and absorb the heat reflected by the earth's surface and radiate it back.
Greenhouse Effect	The effect induced by greenhouse gases, which absorb 90% of earth's radiated heat and reflect it back, thereby slowing the process of heat loss and creating a blanket of insulation.
Heat Island Effect	The warming of local climate due to the human made materials used in urban environments such as concrete, which absorbs and emits more heat compared to natural surfaces like tree cover and vegetation.

Summary and Key Insights

Causes and Impacts of Climate Change:

- a. This part explains how human activities, particularly since modern industrialization, have accelerated greenhouse gas emissions. While natural causes also influence the climate, burning of fossil fuels and deforestation have increased such emissions in the atmosphere.
- b. Increased concentration of greenhouse gases, especially carbon dioxide, has led to an intensifying greenhouse effect, which has contributed to accelerated global warming. These gases absorb almost 90% of the heat radiated by the earth's surface in the form of infrared and then re-radiate it, thereby slowing the process of heat loss to space.
- c. Report highlights the impacts of climate change. While extreme heat, sea level rise, increased flooding risks, and more frequent extreme weather events are primary impacts, secondary impacts include land degradation, poor air quality, migration, and loss of livelihoods.

The dual role of Cities as Contributors and Sufferers:

- a. Rural areas also contribute to the current rate of climate change, but several studies indicate that it is the urban areas that are the highest contributors. City systems have been identified as one of the key systems that are responsible for about 90% of global GHG emissions.
- b. A 2018 study covering around 13,000 cities globally observed that just 100 cities (out of which 19 were small and mid-sized) drive 18% of the emissions.
- c. Within the city system, several sectors emit GHGs; however, it is the energy sector that accounts for over three-quarters of the emissions.
- d. Simultaneously, cities are also among the worst sufferers, experiencing adverse impacts induced by climate change. As per a report in 2022, out of 998 cities worldwide, approximately 80% reported experiencing at least one climate disaster.

Vulnerability of Indian Cities:

- a. According to a 2021 study, 99 of the 100 most vulnerable cities in the world were in Asia, with India having 43 on this list.
- b. India is also home to 13 of the world's riskiest cities, which also include small and mid-sized cities like Agra.
- c. India's urban centres are responsible for nearly 44% of carbon emissions. This is due to a heavy reliance on meeting energy demands through coal, oil, and solid biomass.
- d. In 2023, Indian cities experienced extreme weather events on 318 days out of 365 days, which also resulted in 3,287 deaths. This highlights the urgent need for cities to prepare for disasters and strengthen infrastructure to withstand growing climate extremes.

Contextualising Smaller Cities in Climate Change

Understanding the term

Climate is defined as the average of weather conditions or patterns (such as temperature, wind, cloud cover, and precipitation) for a particular region that occurs for a long period of time, usually 30 years. Climate change is the shift in these average conditions. By definition, climate change refers to the long term shifts in temperature and weather patterns for a particular region from their average (also known as normal) weather patterns.

Even though the consequences of climate change have become the biggest modern day challenge, climate change itself is not a product of the modern era. The reason behind the occurrence of the phenomenon can be natural, but the rate of occurrence has definitely been altered due to the

developments in the modern era. Evidence from scientific studies suggests that climate change has occurred at an unparalleled rate since the mid-20th century, mainly due to human activities that led to the expansion of the greenhouse effect. Earth's climate has changed many times throughout history and will continue to do so in the future. The shifts in climate also occur naturally due to variations in the solar cycle or the amount of solar energy received (which is attributed to variations in the earth's orbit).

The last 800 thousand years have seen 8 cycles of ice ages and warmer periods- the last one being the ice age that marked the beginning of human civilization some 11,700 years ago.

Cities across the world **are suffering from over lapping Climate change induced crisis** such as rising temperature, sea level rise, air pollution, and extreme weather events like droughts, floods, and heatwaves.

Source : Reuters; Vox; The Hans India; WHO; Hindustan Times; The Conversation; Outlook India

Main driver of Climate change

The Earth's atmosphere is composed of various gases, water vapors, and dust particles. This composition- except for the three major components of nitrogen, oxygen, and argon- is not static and keeps changing according to time and place. Some of these gases in the atmosphere absorb the heat reflected by the earth's surface and radiate it back to the earth. These are known as greenhouse gases (GHC) and include: Carbon dioxide (CO₂), Methane (CH₄), Water vapor, Ozone (O₃), Nitrous oxide (N₂O), and Chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs).

It is observed that these gases absorb almost 90% of the heat radiated by the earth's surface in the form of infrared and then re-radiate it, thereby slowing the process of heat loss to space. In simple words, they create a blanket of insulation, which keeps our planet warm. This process of heat getting trapped in the earth's atmosphere is called the greenhouse

effect. Like climate change, the greenhouse effect is also a natural phenomenon that maintains a comfortable climate on earth for life to thrive.

It is the increased warming due to this greenhouse effect that is causing our climate to change more rapidly. The rapid industrialization has increased the concentrations of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere, which has led to accelerated global warming (an increase in the earth's temperature), thereby accelerating the rate of climate change.

Apart from the greenhouse effect, deforestation and concretization (roads, pavements, roofs, and buildings) also contribute to the warming effect. The traditional human made materials used in urban environments reflect less solar energy and absorb & emit more heat compared to natural surfaces like tree cover and vegetation, leading to the warming of the local climate, also called the heat island effect. Changes in Earth's orbit and rotation, variations in solar

Figure 2: Contribution of greenhouse gases in warming

Source : Drivers of climate change as taken from the Summary for Policymakers of the sixth IPCC assessment report

Carbon Dioxide is the biggest contributor to the warming caused by greenhouse gases.

radiation, and volcanic activity are some other natural causes of climate change that occur at a much slower rate compared to what is happening today. The current rate of climate change is largely attributed to human influence through the release of greenhouse gases.

Findings from studies related to the warming influence indicate carbon dioxide (CO₂)- the primary greenhouse gas- as the biggest contributor to the rise in the earth's temperature among other greenhouse gases. The gas is responsible for a warming of 0.8 degrees Celsius from 1850-1900 to 2010-2019. The rise in CO₂ concentrations is said to be directly proportional to the rise in global temperatures. For every 10 parts per million (ppm) rise in CO₂ concentrations, the mean global temperature rises by 0.1 degrees Celsius. The CO₂ concentration of 10 ppm means that one million air molecules contain 10 molecules of CO₂.

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change Sixth (IPCC's) Sixth Assessment report 2021 finds that greenhouse gas emissions due to human activities have already increased the global average temperature by 1.1 degrees Celsius since pre-industrial times, and it is further expected to rise to 1.5 degrees Celsius in the next few decades.

Primary and Secondary impacts of Climate change on cities

As stated previously, climate change alters the average weather conditions a place has experienced for a long period of time. This simply means that climate change affects the duration and intensity of seasons and may amplify some aspects of climate, such as heat, precipitation events, and sea level rise in cities.

Extreme Heat is a primary impact of climate change, **while water scarcity is a secondary impact** caused due to this primary impact.

Source : The Indian Express; Carbon Copy

Figure 3 : Climate change manifests itself in the form of primary & secondary impacts at city level

Source : Causes and Effects of Climate Change; Impacts of Climate Change; The effects of climate change | UN; EPA; myclimate

The consequences of climate change can manifest in different ways at the city level and can be classified as primary and secondary impacts. Primary impacts refer to the direct consequences of climate change on the normal weather conditions of a city and related climatic events, while Secondary impacts are defined as the effects that climate change has on the citizens and the urban ecosystem of a city through the primary impacts.

I. Primary impacts-

- a. Rise in temperatures:** Increase in annual average of minimum and maximum temperatures
- b. Extreme Heat:** Increase in number of heatwave days
- c. Rise in Sea Level:** Increase in temperature has caused the sea level to rise, putting coastal cities at risk of getting submerged.
- d. Increased Risk of Flooding:** Increase in heavy precipitation events and sea level

rise has increased the risk of flooding, especially river and coastal flooding

e. Extreme weather events: Increasing risk of droughts; decrease in summer precipitation with increase in unseasonal heavy precipitation events; accelerated warming increases the risk of extreme winter events; and increased frequency of intense cyclonic events

II. Secondary impacts-

- a. Poor Air Quality:** Increase in the concentration of pollutants due to warming climate
- b. Increased risk of Wildfires:** Increase in extreme heat and rise in summer temperatures have increased the risk of wildfires.
- c. Land degradation and water scarcity:** Extreme weather events, droughts in particular, cause land to degrade as they decrease the soil's ability to store carbon and also lead to water scarcity.

d. Declining Biodiversity: Changes in weather patterns have shifted the distribution of species, and with rising temperatures and extreme weather events, flora and fauna are also at risk of extinction

e. Increasing health issues and deaths: Increase in respiratory and cardiovascular disease due to poor air quality, deaths and injuries related to extreme weather events, and threat to food and water security

f. Loss of livelihood and property damage: Increased risk of flooding and rise in extreme weather events have devastating impacts on physical infrastructure, thereby affecting the livelihood of the residents

g. Migration: Displacement of people due to adverse consequences of primary climate change impacts

Primary impacts like melting glaciers, loss of sea ice, rise in sea levels, and intense heat waves, which were already predicted over 10 years ago, are now visible. Scientists are now warning about the severe irreversible weather damages and consequent secondary impacts that the earth will experience if humans continue to add greenhouse gases. Changes like extreme weather events, wildfires, and water scarcity, among others, are already occurring faster than expected.

Figure 4: Dual role of cities in Climate change: Cities as Contributors and Cities as Sufferers

Source : Various sources

The dual role of cities in Climate change

Almost all of the cities across the globe suffer from at least one of the above mentioned impacts of climate change. However, the role that cities play in this phenomenon is not just limited to sufferers. Being centres of human activity, cities are also the prime contributors to climate change. Human activity has accelerated the rate of climate change since the 1950s. Scientists suggest that it is extremely likely (more than 95%) that human activities have been the dominant cause of more than half of modern global warming.

A. Cities as contributors to climate change:

The World Bank's Climate Change Action Plan (2021–2025) identifies city systems as one of the five key systems that generate almost 90% of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Findings reveal that the global share of emissions from urban areas has seen an increase of around 5% to 10% from 2015 to 2020. Urban emissions increased from 25 GtCO₂-eq (Gigatonne Carbon Dioxide equivalent) in 2015 to 29 GtCO₂-eq in 2020.

A 2018 study covering around 13,000 cities across the globe observed that just 100 cities drive 18% of global emissions. Interestingly, the top 10 list not only includes bigger cities like Seoul, New York, Chicago, and Dubai but also includes 19 small and mid-sized ones – cities with population up to 2.5 million – like Huhot, Boston, Seattle, Doha, and Abu Dhabi. Small and mid-sized cities take top positions in the list of higher per capita footprint as well – 7 of the top 10 are small and mid-sized.

More than 75% of the global greenhouse

Figure 5 : Cities as contributors to climate change
 Source : IPCC Report 2022; Global Gridded Model of Carbon Footprints study; IEA- CO₂ Emissions in 2022

gas emissions come from the energy sector, and it is important to note that cities are responsible for around three-quarters of energy related carbon dioxide emissions. As per the International Energy Agency's analysis, global carbon dioxide emissions from energy combustion and industrial processes recorded an all time high and accounted for 89% of the total energy related greenhouse gas emissions.

B. Cities as sufferers of climate change:

Cities are also suffering from various impacts of climate change. Some are becoming hotter and drier, while others are at risk of getting submerged. 2023 was earth's warmest year on record, while 2022 was earth's sixth warmest year since 1880.

Currently, around 200 million city dwellers in over 350 cities live with summer temperature highs of over 35°C. This number is expected to increase to 970 cities by 2050. Some small and mid-sized cities recorded summer temperatures above 45°C in 2022 across the globe. These include Banda in India (49°C), Roebourne in Australia (50.5°C), Jacobabad in Pakistan (51°C) and Phoenix in Arizona (45.6°C).

In 2022, the global mean sea level also set a new record high of 101.2 mm above 1993 levels. At present, 267 million people live on land less than 2 metres above sea level. Over 570 coastal cities around the world, with an estimated population of 800 million, are vulnerable to a 0.5m rise by 2050. The 2050 Climate Change City Index ranked cities by their vulnerability to sea level rise flooding. The index found that five small and mid-sized cities, along with larger cities, were among the top 10 most vulnerable. Amsterdam was ranked as the second most vulnerable city. By 2100, global sea levels are expected to rise to 1.1m and around 630 million people are expected to live on land below projected annual flood levels.

Climate change is projected to result in 5 million additional deaths annually worldwide, with the latest research indicating that this number could rise to 83 million excess deaths by 2100. In addition to the human suffering and ecological devastation it causes, climate change also leads to significant economic losses. Over the past decade alone, climatic disasters have resulted in direct damages totaling 1.3 trillion dollars. By 2050, the global economy is expected to suffer a GDP loss of approximately 11% to 14% due to climate change, equating to around 23 trillion dollars.

Figure 6 : Cities as sufferers of climate change
 Source : News reports; 2050 Climate Change City Index; A study by CDP Global

In 2022, there were 10 Climate related disasters, each resulting in damages worth over 3 billion dollars. As per a report in 2022, out of the 998 cities worldwide, approximately 80% reported experiencing at least one of these disasters. Pakistan's floods were one of the most devastating extreme weather events of 2022- killed over 1700 people and caused damages worth INR 3.2 trillion. Around 12% of the country was flooded, affecting 15% of its population. Some of the worst affected areas include the following small and mid-sized cities: Qambar, Larkana, Quetta, and Khairpur Nathan Shah.

As per the recent numbers from the international disaster database EM-DAT, 2023 witnessed 240 climate related events, including cyclones, landslides, storms, floods, and wildfires. It further stated that the number of deaths globally due to such events saw a 30% rise from 2022. With a 340% rise, the highest increase was in deaths due to storms.

Indian cities most vulnerable to the impacts of climate change

The Global Climate Risk Index 2021, by Germanwatch (an environmental think tank), ranks India as the 7th most

vulnerable country to climate change. The Climate Vulnerability Index, released by the Council on Energy, Environment and Water (CEEW) in October 2021, revealed that around 80% Indians live in districts prone to climate risks, with Assam, Andhra Pradesh, Maharashtra, Karnataka, and Bihar as the top five states most vulnerable to extreme climate events such as floods, droughts, and cyclones. According to the Environmental Risk Outlook 2021 by Verisk Maplecroft, out of the 100 most vulnerable cities in the world, 99 are in Asia, of which 43 are Indian. India is home to 13 of the world's riskiest cities, which also include small and mid-sized cities like Agra, which stands in 6th place.

In May 2022, Banda in Uttar Pradesh became the hottest city in the state by recording a record high temperature of 49°C. The city is said to have crossed above 45°C four times during the summer season. Around 42 cities across Uttar Pradesh, Rajasthan, Madhya Pradesh, Haryana, Odisha, Punjab, Jharkhand, Andhra Pradesh, and Chhattisgarh reported maximum temperatures above 44°C in 2022.

As per NASA's prediction, at least 12 Indian cities will be submerged by up to 2.7 feet by the end of the century. These cities include: Bhavnagar, Mormugao, Kandla,

Figure 7: Cities at risk as the per Environmental Risk Outlook 2021
 Source : Verisk Maplecroft Global Risk Analytics Dataset | Figure adapted from Bloomberg

Mumbai, Okha, Mangaluru, Paradip, Kochi, Visakhapatnam, Khidirpur, Chennai, and Tuticorin- 10 small and mid-sized cities and 2 big cities. A 2020 report released by CEEW finds that over 75% of districts in India are hotspots for extreme climate events, which include: floods, droughts, and cyclones.

Growing carbon emissions in Indian cities

Even though India's emissions are much lower than the global average, they have been growing continuously. India's urban centres are responsible for nearly 44% of the country's rapidly growing carbon emissions. Around 70% of the GHG emissions come from energy use, as 80% of energy demand is still met by coal, oil, and solid biomass. The map below (data as per a 2018 study) shows that our small and mid-sized urban centres are also contributing a significant amount to these emissions.

To be compatible with the global 1.5°C IPCC scenario, India needs to limit its GHG emissions below 4.597 MtCO₂e (metric tons of carbon dioxide equivalent).

Figure 8 : Number of Indian cities at risk
 Source : Verisk Maplecroft Global Risk Analytics Dataset

Figure 9 : Climate change and Indian cities
 Source : Various Sources

However, the country's Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC) for 2030 would only restrict emissions between 6.034 MtCO₂e and 6.203 MtCO₂e. The 2018 study reveals that some of the small and mid-sized cities in India have produced more carbon emissions than the permissible limit. In Chandigarh, the total carbon emissions were almost twice the limit.

The IPCC's future projects are based on five future scenarios that depend on the actions taken by countries to cut CO₂ emissions. The IPCC's 1.5°C scenario is described as the most optimistic scenario, where global CO₂ emissions are cut to net zero by 2050. It is the only scenario that meets the goal of the Paris Agreement to limit global warming to 1.5°C above pre-industrial levels.

Figure 10: Carbon Emissions of Smaller Indian cities

Source: Global Gridded Model of Carbon Footprints study 2018; citycarbonfootprints.info; Map adapted from Down to Earth

Growing Climate extremes in Indian cities

Indian cities are going to be worst affected by climate change as they are becoming more & more vulnerable to environmental and climate-related risks. These include

deadly heat waves, rising sea levels, extreme rainfall, and extreme weather events like frequent floods, cyclones, and cloud bursts. Indian cities experienced extreme weather events on 314 out of the 365 days in 2022.

This number increased to 318 days out of

365 days in 2023, resulting in 3,287 deaths and damage to 2.21 million hectares of crop area. Of the 318 days, heavy rains, floods, and landslides were recorded on 208 days. The study further reveals that India saw extreme weather events consecutively for 123 days from June to September. Though Himachal Pradesh recorded the highest number of extreme events, it was Bihar that suffered the most in terms of casualties- 642 people lost their lives due to such events.

Many Indian cities, like Shimla and Bhopal, witnessed record breaking temperatures and unbearable heat in 2022. The last decade saw over a 4% increase in the number of heatwave days compared to the previous one. Not just heat waves, but cold wave events have become more frequent in the past decade (2011-2021) with an increase of over 5 days in the average number of cold wave days per decade to even more than 15 days in some parts.

Similarly, extreme rainfall events and their associated disasters, like floods and landslides, have also been on the rise. Heavy rains in Gujarat created flood like situations in many low lying areas like Navsari and Valsad. Many districts in Madhya Pradesh, like Chhindwara, Hoshangabad, Seoni, and Harda, recorded extremely heavy rainfall beyond the threshold limit (20 cm), causing the rivers to overflow. Kullu district in Himachal Pradesh faced landslides triggered by heavy rainfall. The number of stations recording 'extremely heavy rainfall' increased from 261 in 2017 to 554 in 2019. As per CEEW's findings, 55 or more districts have faced extreme flood events each year since 2005. The number of lightning events has also been on the rise. With 18.5 million strikes, April 2020 to March 2021 saw a 34% rise in lightning strikes compared to the previous year.

Indian cities experienced extreme weather events on 318 out of the 365 days in 2023!

Figure 11: Number of days per extreme weather event reported in 2023
 Source: 2023 breaks global warming records | CSE India

Even though climate change is a macro level issue, it manifests itself at the micro or local level, that is, in cities. This chapter dealt with the role that cities play in climate change and attempted to explore the extent to which they are being impacted. The following chapters of this series deal with the individual impacts of

climate change, like poor air quality, rise in temperature, and rise in sea level. These chapters look at how the small and mid-sized Indian cities are being affected by these impacts and what they are doing to manage them.

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